

ROMANTICISM IN WORDSWORTH'S POETRY

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Abstract: It is described that the emergence of English romantic poetry in world literature is related to the traditions of Eastern literature in terms of folklore, ancient literature, artistic form and content. In this article, the harmony of the poetry of William Wordsworth, one of the brightest representatives of the English romantic literature, with the Eastern poetry is analyzed with the help of poetic examples.

Key words: romantic poetry, literature, nature, man, sonnets, lyric ballads, landscape, Eastern poetry

William Wordsworth is one of the prominent representatives of English romantic literature of the 18th century. As a poet of nature and man, a master of landscape, he was more highly valued in his homeland than Byron. According to Pushkin, the poet was one of the first to write about wild nature, full of greatness, beauty and perfection, and called for the protection of its rights. Indeed, when poets throughout the centuries have sung of the ideal of woman, the beautiful woman, in sonnets, Wordsworth chooses the theme of nature. In fact, the theme of nature serves as a ground for the poet to write about love. The image of a woman in Wordsworth's poetry reflects the qualities of shyness, modesty, and mystery. Apparently, the "ideal of nature" is new to Wordsworth's poetry. According to Pushkin, it was one of the leading themes in the literature of the Renaissance. Jean-Jacques Rousseau, who is famous throughout Europe, glorified nature, and before that, the Scottish philosopher David Hume put emotion over reason, and nature over human cognitive abilities. In England, their ideas were continued by William Godwin. Wordsworth continued this. "Drop your chemistry books and read Godwin," he wrote to a friend. Wordsworth deepened this theme. Wordsworth's confession: "Nature is the "anchor" of the purest thoughts, the nurse, counselor and protector of the soul, the soul of my whole moral being." According to Pushkin, the romantics (not only Wordsworth and

Keats, but also Byron and Shelley, who move the social foundations of society) deified. Nature has become a "nanny" and "advisor" for poets, or even a crutch, without which he cannot take a single step: all its manifestations, changes, whims become the "correlation" (correlation) of the poet's mental states. Romantic poetry is a descriptive natural unimagined without an overture.

William Wordsworth was born in one of the most beautiful places in England - the lakeside. The future poet lived in the north-western region, near the border of Scotland - in the area of beautiful mountains and valleys, hills, lakes and yellow rivers. His childhood and teenage years, the period when he was known as a famous poet, were spent in such beautiful corners. This country also brought up poets like Coleridge and Blake, who were later known as poets. Therefore, Francis Jeffery, editor-in-chief of "Edenburgh Reviews" magazine, called these three poets "lake poets". In this Geoffrey was referring to the geographical proximity and friendly relations between the three poets, but the term "lake school" is firmly established. W. Wordsworth lost his mother at the age of eight, and his father a few years later. He will finish the course at Cambridge, but is in no hurry to choose a profession. His poetry began to attract him.

In 1790, Wordsworth went on a hiking trip to the Alps with a friend and went to Paris. He comes back to France a year after graduating from university. This time he hopes for the realization of republican ideals, freedom, equality and fraternity. In this country, fate brings him to meet the only passionate love of his life - a young French woman named Anne Vallon. As the fruit of pure love, their daughter Karolina is born. Shortly before her birth, Wordsworth went to England to persuade her guardians to marry and get the money necessary for family life. Meanwhile, the execution of Louis XVI of Great Britain enters the war against France and cannot return.

Meanwhile, the events in France are getting worse and worse. After the king and queen, the Republicans, the members of the Convention—the revolution devours its children. The Public Rescue Committee in the province and its Commissioners are

brutal, people are executed almost without trial, with suspicion. Only the Thermidorian coup and the execution of Robespierre stop the flywheel of terror.

In 1798, William Wordsworth, together with his friend Samuel Coleridge, published *Lyrical Ballads*, one of the most important books of English Romanticism. The imperative of 'naturalness', naturalness, was evident in this collection, or rather in the part that Wordsworth wrote. At the beginning of the second edition, he formulated the ideal of a poetic language, free of obsolete poetry, close to the speech of ordinary people.

Pushkin was familiar with this program, at least in magazine debates. In the sketch of the article "On the Poetic Syllable" (1827-1828), he writes about the works of Wordsworth and Coleridge, which are "full of deep feelings and poetic thoughts, expressed in the language of an honest common man."

According to Shevyrev, Pushkin, who did not learn English, had already read in the original version of Wordsworth. There is good reason to associate "I Visited Again..." with "Tintern Abbey" - one of Wordsworth's most famous poems, whose full title reads: "Lines a few miles from Tintern Abbey, with a second visit to the banks of the Wye 13 July 1798".

Already in the name, its main word revisiting - "again visit" - reads the beginning of Pushkin's sieve. The first lines of Wordsworth and Pushkin are led by the theme of love and nature in the Poet's poetry. In fact, one of the main themes of romantic literature is love.

Ты все молчишь! Как быстро отцвела
Твоя любовь, не выдержав дыханья
Разлуки, растоптав воспоминанья,
Отвергла долг и дар свой отняла¹.

Но в горький плен мой разум ты взяла,

Тебе служить — иного нет желанья!

И хоть сожгла ты прошлое дотла,

Душа, как нищий, просит подаянья.

The poet of nature and man, the best master of landscape - William Wordsworth is considered a poet much higher than Byron in his homeland. Two contrasting images of Wordsworth emerged from the young romantic with a revolutionary mood, Keats and Shelley, the elder-student who forgot his idols and freedom. The poet was the first to call for the protection of the rights of wild nature full of greatness, beauty and perfection.

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